

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Toward a cochlear implant electrode array with shape memory effect for post-insertion perimodiolar positioning

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Abstract

For cochlear implants (CI) a final position of the electrode array (EA) along the inner wall of the spirally shaped cochlea is considered to be beneficial because it results in a closer proximity to the auditory nerve fibers. A shape memory effect (SME) could facilitate such shift of the EA toward the cochlear inner wall, but its implementation remains to be solved. The current study presents an EA prototype featuring the SME with minute adjustments of the material properties of Nitinol, a shape memory alloy, in combination with a suitable cooling strategy to prevent premature curling. Ten samples were successfully inserted by a CI surgeon into an artificial cochlear model submerged into a temperature-controllable water bath to simulate temporary hypothermia of the inner ear (31°C). Gentle insertions were possible, with an average insertion speed of 0.81 ± 0.14 mm/s. After recovery of body temperature, the desired position shift toward the modiolus was observed in all trials. Angular insertion depth increased by approximately $81.8^\circ \pm 23.4^\circ$. We demonstrate for the first time that using the body temperature responsive SME for perimodiolar EA positioning is feasible and does not impede a gentle surgical insertion.

KEYWORDS

austenite finish temperature, modiolus hugging electrode, nickel titanium alloy, nitinol, shape memory alloy, smart material, transformation temperature range

1 | INTRODUCTION

A cochlear implant (CI) is a neuroprosthesis that serves for audiological rehabilitation and has become the standard of care for patients with severe to profound hearing loss. Its success story has led to an expansion of implantation criteria, including patients with more residual hearing.^{1,2} When residual hearing is preserved postoperatively, patients can benefit from bimodal electroacoustic stimulation.^{3,4} This

requires that the electrode array (EA) of the CI system is inserted into the scala tympani (ST) of the cochlea without any trauma.

To help minimize contact forces to the intracochlear tissues and reduce trauma, thin and flexible EAs have been designed.^{5,6} Furthermore, a lower incidence of intracochlear scalar translocation (i.e., trauma to the basilar membrane) is reported with use of so-called straight EAs.^{7,8} These EAs follow the cochlea's lateral wall during insertion and remain in this position (i.e., resting against the lateral wall) after insertion is completed. However, a final position of the EA closer to the inner wall is in closer proximity with the nerve fibers of the auditory nerve located in the central axis of the cochlea (also

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known as “modiolus”). Since the modiolus is the target structure for the electric stimulation via the EA, this final position along the modiolus has been considered by some as advantageous.^{9,10}

Commercially available EAs designed to hug the modiolar wall are fabricated in a spiral shape and referred to as “pre-curved” or “perimodiolar” EAs. To enter the cochlea, these pre-curved EAs need to be kept temporarily in a straight configuration using an embedded stiffening wire (i.e., stylet) or a surrounding sheath. The perimodiolar positioning then takes place with the removal of the stylet and the simultaneous inherent spring back effect of the EA, also referred to as “memory” effect. This return movement of a spring-like structure is caused by the stored elastic energy and should not be confused with the shape memory effect (SME).

The fundamental mechanism of the SME is a phase transformation and can be seen for example in near-equiatomic NiTi alloys (a.k.a. Nitinol) between a low-temperature phase called “martensite” and a high-temperature phase called “austenite.”^{11,12} While austenite is stiff and springy, martensite is soft and malleable,¹² facilitating plastic deformation. The SME can be activated by a change in temperature: when heating over the “transformation temperature range” (TTR) the material converts to the austenite phase and recovers the original, pre-determined shape.¹² The TTR is described by characteristic transformation temperatures: a given shape change starts at the austenite start temperature (A_s) and is completed at the austenite finish temperature (A_f). These properties could be applied in the field of EA design (Figure 1) in order to achieve hugging of the modiolar wall.

This idea was first described in the late 1990s^{13,14} and appears simple, as summarized by Spelman et al.¹⁴:

“At below human body temperature the shape memory material would be quite malleable and flexible, allowing it to be inserted a preliminary distance. [...] Finally, when it is completely installed and warmed to body temperature, it will assume the shape of the scala tympani but in a form tight enough so that it will contact the interior modiolar wall [...]”

However, applying this concept to the field of CI surgery is very challenging and mastery of the temperature-induced shape change during the insertion of an EA remains to be solved. First, a fundamental decision must be made on how to activate the thermal SME: either by applying external energy (e.g., resistance heating, inductive heating, additional heating elements),^{15,16} or by using the environmental temperature, i.e. the body temperature (T_b).¹⁷ The present study addresses the latter principle (herein referred to as “passive” heating) and reports on the incorporation of the shape memory effect to a CI electrode array (referred to as SMEA in the following).

Beside different nonlinear effects involved during processing and thermal treatment of the Nitinol wires,¹⁸ the inseparable dependency of different material parameters,¹² and the small EA dimensions with its vulnerability for impact on the mechanical properties during handling, there are fundamental challenges when developing a passive SMEA:

FIGURE 1 Concept illustration: a cochlea implant electrode array (EA) integrated with a spirally shaped Nitinol wire (“inlay”) that in its martensite phase could facilitate a straight-shape for the insertion (A, B) and once the insertion is completed retake its original austenitic shape (C, D). Subfigures (A) and (C) by courtesy of Cochlear Ltd., Sydney, Australia

First: Precise setting of A_f temperature is mandatory. Unlike other applications of Nitinol using the superelastic condition at body temperature and for which wires with A_f in a wide range (typically within $[0^\circ\text{C}; 18^\circ\text{C}]$) are suitable,¹¹ our application requires an A_f very close or equal to T_b , being a fundamental constraint reducing the solution space. Phase transformation needs to be completely finished at T_b to ensure a full shape recovery for optimal perimodiolar placement.

Second: A_s and its relationship to T_b is also highly relevant. To prevent a premature start of curling—which would limit insertion of the SMEA into the cochlea, A_s needs to be as high as possible because the deeper areas within the mastoid cavity are warmer and approach T_b more. Therefore, a narrow TTR is required.

Third: The TTR is affected by external loads, meaning transformation temperatures of pure Nitinol wires determined in “free recovery” conditions will be increased if the shape memory effect is used to deform the surrounding EA (“constrained recovery”). Consequently, transformation temperatures of the final SMEA prototype strongly depend on *both* the material properties of the NiTi wire *and* the stiffness properties of the EA—both components cannot be developed independently from each other.

Furthermore, it is known that the negligible insulating effect of the silicone body does not prevent the Nitinol wire (referred to as “inlay” in the following) from premature heating and subsequent

premature shape change. This is a detrimental factor when considering a slow and gentle insertion of the EA, as necessary in atraumatic CI surgery. Therefore, different strategies to better control the environmental temperature are warranted. In the context of atraumatic or hearing preservation CI surgery, the so called “under water technique” (UWT) fills the mastoid cavity with water in order to minimize pressure variations due to opening of the inner ear.¹⁹ Although originally performed with Ringer solution at body temperature, this concept could be transferred to use a slightly colder fluid that could prevent the SMEA from premature curling. Other investigations aiming to achieve a state of hypothermia as a means to inhibit the inflammatory response resulting from the EA insertion have shown that the cochlea itself can be cooled down.^{2,19,20} An intracochlear drop of temperature of approximately $4.6^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $3.4^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the round window or the apex of the cochlea, respectively have been reported when using a custom-made cooling-probe.^{21,22} In a more recent in vitro study, irrigation fluid at 24.1°C cooled the basal turn of the cochlea down to 30.6°C and when using ice water (5.3°C) the intracochlear temperatures reached 21.0°C .²³

Therefore, if the environmental or T_b could be controlled to stay temporary within a specific cooler temperature range, one would speculate that a SMEA (in a temporary straight configuration) could be introduced into the cochlea. The present study demonstrates for the first time the feasibility of such approach by prototyping a SMEA undergoing insertions into a cochlea model in order to test: a) adjustments of the material properties, b) a suitable cooling strategy to prevent premature curling, c) the prevention of undesirable premature curling during surgically feasible insertion speeds, and d) the desired lateral wall to perimodiolar position shift.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Prototyping

Geometry of the SMEA prototype was based on the typical design of a standard lateral wall EA,⁵ having a length of 18.5 mm and an outer diameter that tapers from 1.2 to 0.5 mm at the tip. The usual pads and wires for electrical stimulation were not included, as the audiological functionality was not intended at this early phase. The surrounding silicone sheath was selected to roughly replicate the stiffness properties of a commercial EA.²⁴

2.1.1 | Designing and processing of the NiTi inlay

Using data of an average sized human scala tympani (with A- and B-values of 9.3 mm and 6.87 mm, respectively) the final shape of the Nitinol inlay was designed to fit to a perimodiolar position. The process of determining these dimensions and model has been described in detail²⁵ and is summarized in Figure 2.

By use of a computer aided design (CAD) software (Inventor Professional, Autodesk Inc., San Rafael, USA) the shape of the inlay was designed to fit to the inner wall of the virtual scala tympani model. A small gap between the model's inner wall and the spiral path was considered to account for the silicone sheath that will surround the inlay. The spiral path was synthesized by six circular arcs with decreasing radii toward the tip, $r_i \geq 1.0$ mm with $i \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$, and tangential transition. A straight segment was added to the wire to cover the basal portion of the cochlea.

FIGURE 2 (A–D) Schematic of designing the inlay geometry: Scala tympani was segmented in rotating mid-modiolar slice planes in steps of 22.5° to generate a 3D model. The corresponding footprint was generated by projecting into the basal plane and used to design the spiral shape of the NiTi wire. (E) CAD drawing showing the dimensions of the designed inlay. (F) 3D model of the silicone sheath in its desired final position in close proximity to the inner wall of the virtual cochlea model. There is a remaining gap between the surface of the silicone sheath and the model's wall due to the irregular angular shape change of the inner wall which was not perfectly remodeled by the circular arcs of the inlay. (G) Fabricated NiTi inlay. (H) SMEA prototype with inlay embedded into the custom silicone sheath. Intracochlear length (marker to tip) is 18.5 mm. Coloring of the sample was omitted for this picture to allow visibility of the inlay. Size of the scale bar is 2 mm.

NiTi inlays were fabricated by G.RAU GmbH & Co. KG (Pforzheim, Germany). The received NiTi rod (SE508) was drawn through a series of dies with decreasing diameters until the final wire diameter of 100 μm was reached. Thermal processing was applied to adjust the TTR of the NiTi wires while a metal fixture was used for shape setting. After final heat treatment the oxide layer was removed chemically. When trimming the wire, a straight segment was added to improve handling during the subsequent SMEA prototyping steps. Transformation temperatures were determined by use of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Discovery DSC25, TA instruments, New Castle, DE, USA). In contrast to a standard full-cycle thermogram according to the ASTM F2004 standard, cooling down from 100°C was interrupted at 0°C and then heated back to 100°C. This captures only the phase transformation that correspond to the planned application where prototypes would be straightened in ice water and heated to body temperature.

As iterative process 16 parameter sets for the thermal processing were tested until a sufficient TTR was found with both A_s and A_f fulfilling the above-mentioned requirements. Three batches of inlays were produced to investigate reproducibility of the inlay fabrication and processing procedures. Only inlays from the first batch were used for further prototyping of the SMEAs.

2.1.2 | SMEA Sample Fabrication

The silicone sheath was produced injecting a liquid silicone elastomer (Sylgard 184, Dow Silicones Deutschland GmbH, Wiesbaden,

Germany) into a two-piece aluminum mold, which delineated the desired outer shape of the SMEA prototype. A thin silicone tube (RCT Reichelt Chemietechnik GmbH & Co, Heidelberg, Germany) with an approximate outer diameter of 0.7 mm and an inner diameter of 0.3 mm was placed in the mold to provide a lumen for the NiTi inlay. Base and crosslinker of the silicone elastomer were mixed (10:1) and afterward degassed using a desiccator at 100 mbar. The silicone was then cured in an oven (UF30, Memmert GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Germany) at 100°C for 3 h. Afterward, the silicone sheath was cut to a total length of 34.5 mm, with 18.5 mm covering the intracochlear portion. Finally, the first 0.5 mm of the lumen was filled with silicone to close it. For improved visibility during the insertion trials, samples were colored using a black marker.

2.2 | BFR Test

To investigate the temperature-dependent shape change a bend and free recovery (BFR) test bench was developed (Figure 3). The setup is a modification of the ASTM F2082 standard, which only works for straight wires. In contrast, our setup is suitable for curved wires and probes, inspired by the work of Undisz et al.²⁶ The sample (e.g., the blank NiTi inlay, SMEA) was mounted onto a sample holder while showing the spiral shape to ensure correct orientation within the test bench. The grasped sample was then manually straightened while being immersed into a separate water bath filled with ice water (approx. 0°C). The water inside the BFR setup was heated up to 60°C at a rate of 1 K/min.

FIGURE 3 (A) Bend and free recovery (BFR) test setup. It consists of a digital heating thermostat (1, Lauda ET 20G, Lauda Dr. R. Wobser GmbH & Co. KG, Lauda-Königshofen, Germany), a water bath for tempering the samples (2), and a digital microscope camera (3, Dino-Lite Universal Edge, Dino-Lite Europe, Almere, Netherlands) in front of the sample (4) in order to enable a non-contact visual method for capturing the temperature-dependent shape change. Water temperature and shape changes were recorded simultaneously with an image acquisition rate of 3 images/s. Two samples can be measured simultaneously. A white sheet with imprinted reference grid served as image background. (B) Close-up view of a SMEA prototype near to its final shape. The inlay is manually retraced in this picture to increase visibility

FIGURE 4 (A–E) Image sequence depicting the shape change of a pure inlay (#09) when being heated in the BFR test. In (E), showing the inlay at its A_f temperature, the five reference points were added as an overlay; being located at the tip of the sample following the quadrants of the wire's spiral shape. (F) Same inlay as in (E) but embedded in the transparent silicone sheath. The composite structure does not reach the same final shape in comparison to the bare NiTi inlay shown in (E) due to the stiffness of the sheath. In addition, A_f is shifted toward higher temperatures due to the external load.

FIGURE 5 Insertion test bench. A heated water bath (1) was used to control the temperature inside the aSTM (2) and a microscope camera (3, Dino-Lite Universal Edge, Dino-Lite Europe, Almere, Netherlands) in front of the cochlear lumen captured the insertion process. A holder was designed for diagonal mounting of the aSTM to enable a more realistic and ergonomic insertion direction

Using the image stacks, A_s was determined as the point where the tip of the initially straight sample has reached a distance of 3.5 mm from the straight reference line. This slightly bended shape was considered as sufficient “straight” to still reach and enter the cochlea. A_f temperature was determined as the point where no further shape change was visible. Therefore, five selected points defined in

the final image with full shape recovery (at approx. 60°C) were manually identified throughout the image stack (Figure 4). Once a part of the sample achieved the final position, the corresponding temperature was noted. The median of these five values was considered as a robust measure for A_f while the maximum value indicates the definite end of the shape change and is considered as an indicator for the accuracy of this method.

2.3 | Experimental evaluation

2.3.1 | Insertion test bench

The test bench setup consists of an artificial scala tympani model (aSTM) milled out of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and covered with a transparent sheet of acrylic glass. As the final shape of the SMEA prototypes showed a less tightly spiral than the designed inlay, we had to slightly adapt the geometry of the aSTM by scaling (1.2×) the original geometry used for inlay design. The aSTM was immersed into the water bath (Thermomix 1419, B. Braun, Melsungen, Germany) to simulate the intracochlear fluid and to control its temperature (Figure 5). Temperature inside the aSTM was measured before and after insertions and all insertion trails were video recorded.

2.3.2 | Study protocols

To answer different questions, two sets of insertion experiments were conducted. First, a single SMEA prototype (#01) was inserted 18 times to investigate the stability and reproducibility of the SME. In addition, a second set of experiments with larger sample size was conducted to investigate the insertability of the SMEAs and their intracochlear behavior. As variability in fabrication of the SMEA prototypes was expected, 14 samples were produced, of which 13 underwent BFR testing (one was rejected as straightening was not possible). Then using the TTR values nine SMEAs that best fitted to T_b were

FIGURE 6 (A) To investigate the distance of the SMEA prototype the model was divided into 8 segments visualized as an overlay (with $\overline{MP_1}$ in parallel to the surface of the aSTM). Distances $\overline{MP_i}$ (with $i = 1...8$) from the modiolus (M) to the inner wall were measured. In addition the corresponding distances to the inner contour of the SMEA prototype in its lateral wall condition (B, $P_{i,l}$) and its final shape (C, $P_{i,f}$) were determined. Subfigures B and C also depict how angular insertion depth was measured starting from the entry point of the SMEA into the cochlear lumen

TABLE 1 Specific values of the produced NiTi wires (inlays) as determined using the interrupted DSC cycle

	Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 3	Precision
Number	15	30	30	
Austenite start temperature $^{DSC}A_{s,Inlay}$	30.9°C	30.9°C	31.0°C	± 0.05 K
Austenite peak temperature $^{DSC}A_{p,Inlay}$	32.4°C	32.4°C	32.5°C	± 0.05 K
Austenite finish temperature $^{DSC}A_{f,Inlay}$	34.1°C	34.1°C	34.2°C	± 0.05 K
$^{DSC}TTR_A$	3.2 K	3.2 K	3.2 K	
Average diameter \bar{D}	92.0 μm	92.1 μm	92.3 μm	± 0.15 μm
$\Delta(D_{max} - D_{min})$	2 μm	2 μm	1 μm	

selected based on the median $^{BFR}A_f \leq 38.1^\circ\text{C}$ and the nine lowest values for maximum $^{BFR}A_f$. Including the results from #01 a sample size of ten was achieved for the second experiment set.

All insertion experiments were conducted as follows: the water bath was set to 31°C to simulate hypothermia in the cochlea while the SMEA prototype was immersed in ice water (approx. 0°C) and manually straightened using tweezers. The straight sample was inserted into the aSTM by a trained CI surgeon, aiming for a slow and gentle movement as in hearing preservation surgery. After completion of insertion, the water bath was heated up to body temperature (37°C) to terminate the temporary hypothermia in the experiment. Body temperature was held for at least 15 min to ensure even heat distribution inside the aSTM. Videos of the insertion process were evaluated to estimate the average insertion speed. Angular insertion depth and distance of the SMEA prototype to the inner wall of the model were evaluated directly after insertion (cold, lateral wall condition) and after recovery of body temperature (warm, perimodiolar condition) using a method depicted in Figure 6. In case of technical problems, insertion of the same sample was repeated until the insertion process could be finished for the first time.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Inlay and sample fabrication

A total of 75 inlays were fabricated. Table 1 illustrates the reproducibility of the inlay fabrication procedure including thermal treatment

for shape- and TTR setting. Precision of transformation temperature setting was found to be less than 0.1 K; average $^{DSC}A_s$ was 30.9°C while $^{DSC}A_f$ was 34.1°C leading to a ^{DSC}TTR of 3.2 K.

Table 2 summarizes the results of the BFR tests. Average $^{BFR}A_{s,Inlay}$ and $^{BFR}A_{f,Inlay}$ of the first batch of inlays was $(17.2 \pm 2.3)^\circ\text{C}$ and $(33.4 \pm 0.4)^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Accounting for all 14 produced samples, the average $^{BFR}A_{s,SMEA}$ and $^{BFR}A_{f,SMEA}$ was found to be $(15.8 \pm 3.6)^\circ\text{C}$ and $(37.5 \pm 0.9)^\circ\text{C}$, respectively; this indicated an acceptable reproducibility. A_f of the SMEA prototypes was (4.1 ± 1.0) K higher than of the pure NiTi wires.

3.2 | Experimental evaluation: insertion trials

Sample #01 was used for 18 insertions. Nine of these insertions were considered successful, since they allowed a smooth insertion up to the final insertion depth. Average insertion speed was (0.72 ± 0.19) mm/s (range: 1.03–0.40 mm/s, Table 3). Technical problems were observed in the other nine insertion trials: in two trials the tip of the prototype was already bent when reaching the opening of the aSTM so that insertion could not be started; in the remaining seven trials, a wrong orientation of the inlay inside the silicone dummy was observed, attributed to an unrecognized rotation of the inlay during manual straightening.

Directly after insertion, the SMEA prototypes showed a mid-scalar position in the basal part of the aSTM followed by direct contact to the lateral wall in the region around 180° of angular insertion depth. Toward the tip, distance to the modiolus decreases again due

Sample	BFR _{A_s,Inlay}	BFR _{A_f,Inlay}		BFR _{A_s,SMEA}	BFR _{A_f,SMEA}		Shift	S1	S2
		Median	Max		Median	Max			
#01	19.7	33.2	33.5	11.9	36.7	39.2	3.5	x	x
#02	18.7	33.5	35.6	12.6	36.6	40.1	3.1		x
#03	19.4	32.8	33.7	14.2	37.8	43.9	5.0		
#04	16.9	33.6	34.7	11.9	37.2	40.9	3.6		x
#05	18.2	33.1	34.4	16.4	39.1	41.1	6.0		
#06	17.0	34.1	34.1	11.3	36.6	39.4	2.5		x
#07	19.0	33.2	33.5	18.9	37.7	40.3	4.5		x
#08	18.9	33.3	33.6	22.1	36.1	39.8	2.8		x
#09	16.4	33.0	33.4	19.1	38.1	40.6	5.1		x
#10	14.9	34.2	34.5	11.5	38.1	40.6	3.9		x
#11	17.5	33.5	33.9	14.8	36.6	39.0	3.1		x
#12	11.0	33.3	33.6	16.4	38.4	40.8	5.1		
#13	19.2	33.3	34.9	20.2	38.4	39.2	5.1		
#14	15.0	33.7	34.8	-	-	-	-		
#15	15.6	33.7	34.0	20.1	37.1	40.6	3.4		x
n	15	15	15	14	14	14	14	1	10
mean	17.2	33.4	34.1	15.8	37.5	40.4	4.1		
SD	2.3	0.4	0.6	3.6	0.9	1.2	1.0		

Notes: Sample #01 was utilized for the first set of experiments (S1). Column S2 indicates whose samples which have been included in the second study. Sample #14 was rejected due to irregular behavior of the silicone sheath which prohibited sufficient straightening. In column “shift” the difference between $A_{f,Inlay}$ and the median of $A_{f,SMEA}$ is reported which is the amount of increase of A_f due to the mechanical resistance of the silicone sheath (“constrained recovery”). All temperatures in °C.

TABLE 3 Results of multiple insertion of the same SMEA prototype

Label	Insertion speed (mm/s)	Angular insertion depth after insertion (°)	Angular insertion depth after shape change (°)
01-03	0.53	321.3	392.2
01-05	0.84	306.4	394.8
01-06	0.40	290.1	391.8
01-07	0.80	297.6	391.9
01-10	0.69	314.0	384.2
01-11	0.58	284.8	395.8
01-12	0.69	313.3	387.9
01-18	1.03	284.2	395.8
01-20	0.93	279.3	370.7
Mean	0.72	299.0	389.5
SD	0.19	14.4	7.5

Notes: Two trials (01-01, 01-13) only served for setup tests that is why the labels run up to 20 although 18 insertion experiments were conducted.

to both the decreasing width of the aSTM and the beginning of the shape recovery of the inlay, which first occurs at the tip (Figure 6B). Average distance to the inner wall across all measured points was (0.90 ± 0.28) mm for the lateral wall condition. Detailed measures for all segments are provided in Figure 7A. Angular insertion depth was found to be $299.0^\circ \pm 14.4^\circ$; which explains missing values for distances $MP_{1,7}$ and $MP_{1,8}$.

After full recovery of body temperature the desired shape change leading to a perimodiolar position was observed. The average distance to the inner wall decreased to (0.24 ± 0.15) mm across all measured points (Figure 7A). Additionally, angular insertion depth increased to $389.5^\circ \pm 7.5^\circ$, an increase of approximately 90° .

In the second set of the insertion experiments, nine additional samples were used. Seven (78%) samples could be fully inserted in the

TABLE 2 Results of BFR test of all SMEA prototypes

FIGURE 7 Distances between the inner wall of the model and the SMEA prototype measured directly after insertion (blue marker, lateral wall condition, approx. 31°C) and after shape recovery at body temperature (red markers, perimodiolar condition, approx. 37°C). The position of a conventional lateral wall EA is added as a reference (black dots). (A) Study: nine repetitions with the same SMEA prototype. (B) Study 2: 10 different samples, each inserted once

first trial. For the remaining two samples the first attempt to insert was aborted due to technical reasons but a second attempt was successful. The technical problems resulted from the inlay having a wrong orientation inside the silicone sheath (attributed to overlooked rotation during straightening), and in the second case the straightening in the ice water was insufficient and had to be repeated. Hence, from these additional nine samples, a total of 11 insertions was conducted. Considering sample #01 from the previous set of experiments was also successfully inserted on a second attempt, this second experiment set includes in total 13 insertions conducted with 10 samples.

Figure 8 compares the intracochlear position directly after insertion under hypothermia conditions and after restoration of body temperature for all 10 SMEA prototypes. This clearly demonstrates the desired shape change and the consequent shift of the EA toward the modiolus. Average distance between the inner wall of the aSTM and the SMEA prototype was reduced from (0.90 ± 0.30) mm at lower temperatures to (0.27 ± 0.19) mm in the final condition (see Table 4). Figure 7B shows there is a closer proximity to the perimodiolar wall in the regions P2-P3 and P6-P8. In the P4 and P5 regions, a difference between the geometry of the model and the designed inlay geometry (as seen in Figure 2F) leads to a remaining distance of (0.45 ± 0.14) mm and (0.39 ± 0.13) mm, respectively.

In this set of experiments, angular insertion depth increased in average 81° and average insertion speed was (0.81 ± 0.14) mm/s (range: 0.97–0.53 mm/s; Table 4).

4 | DISCUSSION

Straight EAs are considered beneficial in terms of hearing preservation due to their high flexibility and lower likelihood of scalar translocation.^{7,8} A perimodiolar position on the other hand facilitates a closer

proximity to the neural target tissue for electric stimulation. An intracochlear shape change, as e.g. provided by the SME, could offer both advantages but has not yet been developed.

A major challenge to implement a temperature-induced SME in the field of cochlear implants is the correct control and adjustment of the temperature range in which the shape change appears. As there is only a small range between T_b and the appearance of thermal injury, the sufficient “thermal window” is extremely narrow making the design of the shape memory actuator much more sophisticated in comparison to other applications, such as the automotive or aircraft industries. In the passive heating concept both A_f and A_s need to be close to T_b as a fundamental constrain to ensure both full shape recovery after and prevent premature curling during insertion. As the deeper areas within the mastoid cavity are warmer and approach T_b more, the environmental temperature in the operating room (18°C–21°C) is not a reliable condition to preserve the martensite phase until the SMEA is passed through the mastoid and facial recess. Thus, a narrow TTR of only few Kelvins is required and we achieved this in our study with an optimized thermal treatment resulting in a ^{DSC}TTR of only 3.2 K.

However, a narrow TTR based on DSC alone does not solve the problem. Another challenge is, that shape change starts from the tip. Not only premature curling in the mastoid inhibits a successful insertion but also premature bending of the tip within the basal region of the cochlea may cause intracochlear trauma. As it was already known that the insulating effect of the silicone body is insufficient to prevent premature coiling, a strategy to control the environmental temperatures, including the thermal conditions within the inner ear is mandatory. Recent research offers new options for cooling the SMEA either by use of irrigation fluid²³ or a cooling-probe for local hypothermia.^{21,22} Both approaches promise that cooling down the basal turn of the cochlea by several Kelvins will become possible even in an intraoperative setting.

FIGURE 8 Photos of all 10 SMEA prototypes directly after insertion in the aSTM at 31°C (left) and after heating up to body temperature (right). Samples where a second attempt was necessary to achieve full insertion are underlined.

TABLE 4 Results of insertion tests with in total 10 samples

Sample	Insertion speed (mm/s)	Angular insertion depth after insertion (°)	Angular insertion depth after shape change (°)	Increase of angular insertion depth (°)
#01	0.53	321.3	392.2	70.9
#02	0.97	289.3	398.9	109.6
#04	0.71	276.9	361.0	84.1
#06	0.97	251.5	371.0	119.5
#07	0.69	331.0	373.5	42.5
#08	0.71	308.7	371.0	62.3
#09	0.88	291.9	368.4	76.5
#10	0.80	322.3	383.6	61.3
#11	0.93	301.0	385.8	84.8
#15	0.93	278.3	375.0	96.7
Mean	0.81	297.2	378.0	80.8
SD	0.14	23.3	11.1	23.4

Notes: The table lists the calculated insertion speed and the measured angular insertion depth before and after rewarming to body temperature.

A meaningful parameter to describe the efficiency of temperature management and therefore, prevention of premature curling is the speed of insertion. A “slow” insertion speed indicates that the straight configuration is stable enough during sufficient time, enabling the EA to pass the basal turn of the cochlea and to be inserted to a full depth. To the best of our knowledge there is no universal definition which speed values are considered as a slow insertion and this attribute is used differently depending on the context. In case of manual EA insertions insertion speeds between 0.7 and 2.7 mm/s have been observed, with an average of 1.6 mm/s.²⁷ Speed values in the range of 1.1–1.3 mm/s have been rated as “relatively low” by the authors. In another study²⁸ 1.6 mm/s was referred to as “fast,” while 0.25 mm/s was the investigated condition for a “slow” insertion. However, in the same study a range between 0.6 and 1.2 mm/s was found to be the slowest range for “gentle” insertions, that is, a continuous manual forward motion without unintended but unavoidable interruptions. This speed range was referred to as “stable” to distinguish it from the slower but noncontinuous motions. As we have been aiming for manual insertion we consider the slowest possible *continuous* hand motion as the most relevant benchmark for which (0.86 ± 0.32) mm/s are reported.²⁸ Although even slower hand motions on average are possible, they go along with undesired micro-motions, pauses and insertion reversals resulting in short-term, sudden high speed values and thus peak forces that contradict a gentle and atraumatic insertion.²⁰ In our experiments, the average insertion speed was (0.81 ± 0.14) mm/s, which is a value falling on the lower end of what is humanly, manually feasible.²⁸ Therefore, our results corroborate that when SMEA prototypes are subjected to a temporary hypothermia they maintain a straight configuration that is stable enough to facilitate desirable slow insertions performed by a surgeon.

Moreover, the desired post-insertion position change toward the modiolus was clearly demonstrated in our experiments. Distance to the inner wall was substantially reduced along the entire length of the cochlea. Only in the basal region the opening of the aSTM prevented a more perimodiolar placement. Toward the apex the decreasing width of the ST also limits the impact of an intracochlear position change. However, these are anatomical constraints and not related to the SME. The latter may motivate an SMEA in which the NiTi inlay does not go all the way to the tip as one could argue that if the tip of the SMEA is not temperature sensitive and guides the following part into the cochlea, likelihood of premature curling could also be reduced.

An additional anatomical constrain is the variability in the shape of the modiolus. In our study the remaining gap between inner wall of the aSTM and the SMEA in the P4 and P5 region is a good example how an average sized SMEA will fit to an individually shaped cochlea. Modiolus hugging without any gaps will require patient specific design and processing of the inlay which seems unrealistic from both a commercial and a technological point of view.

A positive side-effect of the intracochlear position change is the corresponding increase in angular insertion depth compared to a straight EA with same nominal length but without SME. In contrast to the use of a longer EA to achieve this deeper insertion, we assume

that the post-insertion position shift goes along with a lower risk of intracochlear trauma.

In the current prototype, design parameters of the inlay are optimized for the silicone sheath. A previous study showed the diameter of the inlay is thick and strong enough to bend a commercial EA with up to 22 platinum contacts and wires but also thin enough to avoid a significant additional stiffness that could lead to increased risk of trauma.¹⁷ Other parameters such as A_s , A_f , and the trained shape need to be adapted to the mechanical properties of a specific EA selected for further translational research. Therefore, fine tuning of the parameters for thermal treatment of the NiTi wires to adjust A_s and A_f will be necessary for a commercial EA, as our prototypes do not exactly anticipate their stiffness properties. Also, the final shape of the SMEA does not only depend on the trained shape of the inlay at A_f but also on the mechanical properties of the surrounding structures. The bending forces due to the SME and the opposing forces of the straight-produced EA will lead to an equilibrium of forces that determines the final shape at A_f . Designing an adequately trained shape requires a very detailed knowledge about the (nonlinear) stiffness properties of the EA and necessitate an iterative development process.

During the insertion experiments, some technical problems were observed which led to a failure of the insertion. In most cases, we attributed this to an unintended shift in orientation of the inlay during the straightening procedure. This wrong orientation was possible in our prototypes as the inlay was motile inside the lumen of the silicone sheath. Such an unplanned change in orientation could be prevented in a next-generation prototype, for example, by sealing the inlay. It can be assumed that such a problem can be completely eliminated in a commercial version with highly standardized manufacturing processes in contrast to our limited capability of prototyping including a high proportion of manual labor. Furthermore, in a commercial version a marker (e.g., wing or a comparable feature) of the silicon body can indicate the bending direction of the inlay to ensure correct position of the EA toward the modiolus.¹⁷

All successful insertion with the same prototype demonstrated a remarkable stability and reproducibility of the SME other multiple cycles ($n = 18$) of straightening and curling. Although only a single shape change will be required in clinical routine, the SME reproducibility allows repetition of straightening if premature curling appears before entering the cochlea.

The most limiting factor in our insertion experiments is the cochlear model. Friction conditions of the aSTM are most likely not identical to in vivo conditions, as the surgeon reported a higher occurrence of sticking during the insertion trials. Whether this sensory feedback was rather due to the inherent SMEA bending process cannot be further elucidated with our current methodology. Furthermore, simulating in-vivo thermal conditions of the cochlea and the mastoid cavity by a water tank is associated with major trade-offs but had been used due to lack of better solutions. Heat capacity, heat flow and convection may vary significantly compared with real conditions. Therefore, further experiments in a more realistic cochlear and temporal bone model are necessary to further validate these findings. This should also include further investigation of the cooling, including research questions such

as whether less cooled conditions are sufficient; for example by combining milder local hypothermia with under water insertion. Appropriate cooling strategies may even allow significantly lower insertion speeds as aimed for in robot assisted insertions.^{20,29–32} However, investigating this would require a test stand with automated insertion, which falls outside the scope of this study.

5 | CONCLUSION

To summarize we present evidence on the feasibility of inserting an EA featuring the shape memory effect. Local hypothermia effectively prevented premature curling, enabling insertion speeds of less than 1.0 mm/s in all trials. The post-insertion position shift demonstrates a promising application of this material for CI surgery as it could facilitate an atraumatic insertion with the straight configuration and promises higher performance by bringing the EA closer to the modiolus. To the best of our knowledge, this was the first experimental demonstration of perimodiolar positioning by applying SME passively activated by body temperature.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Katarzyna Plaskonka and Andreas Keck are employees of G.RAU GmbH & Co. KG, a company that manufactures products from different metals and alloys including Nitinol. The authors declare that they have no other conflict of interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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